

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

PROSPECTS FOR ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF UZBEKISTAN WITHIN THE WORLD TRADE ORGANIZATION: ANALYSIS OF MULTILATERAL TRADE AGREEMENTS

Toshpulatova Malika Ulugbek qizi

PhD student at the Institute of Macroeconomic and Regional Studies

ORCID: 0009-0001-1382-7854

Abstract

This article examines the prospects for economic development of Uzbekistan within the framework of the World Trade Organization (WTO) and analyzes the impact of multilateral trade agreements on the national economy. As a country transitioning to a market economy, Uzbekistan's integration into the World Trade System is of great importance for sustainable economic growth. The study analyzes the state of Uzbekistan's trade relations with WTO and EAEU member states over the past five years - imports and exports. The article puts forward proposals to stimulate the country's economic development, increase competitiveness, and address the complexities of global trade dynamics through WTO membership.

Keywords: WTO, Uzbekistan, EAEU, economic growth, export, import

Introduction

The World Trade Organization (WTO) is an influential international organization that coordinates the trading system of world economies. Currently, 166 countries are members of the WTO [12], which account for 98% of global trade [13]. The main task of the WTO is to establish free and transparent trade relations, promote fair competition and strengthen the economic stability of member countries. This task of the WTO fully corresponds to the goal of economic reforms being implemented in Uzbekistan. For developing countries like Uzbekistan, WTO membership is of great importance in bringing trade practices into line with international standards and creating wider access to world markets.

The final result of the country's foreign economic activity, in particular, the reforms being implemented in the field of foreign trade, directly affects the standard of living of the population. As a result of measures taken in recent years to stimulate exports, optimize imports and ensure the balance of foreign trade, the republic's foreign trade turnover in January-September 2024 amounted to 48.2 billion US dollars, which is 3.5 billion US dollars or 7.7% more than in the same period in 2023 [14]. Uzbekistan, through its membership in the WTO, will integrate into the international trading system, and this process will create additional opportunities for promoting exports, expanding the production of import-substituting goods, adapting to international trade standards, and eliminating trade barriers. In turn, WTO membership will give Uzbekistan the opportunity to trade with 166 countries on an equal footing, which will play an important role in strengthening the country's position in the world market. This is a great achievement for Uzbekistan!

Literature review

In their article "On the Impact of GATT/WTO Membership on Trade," Mario Larch, Roberta Piermartini, and V. Yotov state, "In particular, our results show that, on average, accession to GATT and/or WTO increased trade between members by 171 percent and trade between members and non-members by about 88 percent. We also find that, while GATT/WTO has been effective in promoting trade among members, WTO is

more effective in promoting trade with non-members than GATT [1]. M.K. Tang and S.J. Wei noted in their study that "While growth rates typically remain stable for the first five years after accession, WTO membership consistently increases the economy by 20%. Economic growth increases by an average of 2.5 percent for at least five years after a country joins GATT/WTO" [3]. Similarly, according to research by T.L. Allee and J.E. Scalera, "...the more committed a state is to an international organization and the greater the policy change required, the greater the benefits it derives from membership in the organization" [4]. The WTO experience of countries in transition should be considered positive. The agreements significantly improve the stability of market access, they help to eliminate corruption and improve governance without significant losses of state revenues. In addition, Z. Drabek, M. Bacchetta noted that the WTO has also played a positive role in strengthening domestic policies to better manage balance of payments crises [5]. According to G.Felbermayr's research, on average, WTO membership increases bilateral trade by about 40% [6]. T.S.Eicher has argued that WTO membership promotes regional trade integration at the expense of longer-term trade among developing country members [7]. Also, Richard Pomfret, in his study "Uzbekistan and the WTO," noted that "...the answer to the question of whether Uzbekistan should or should not join the WTO depends on its commitment to economic reforms. If the government is serious about replacing its dependence on resource exports and protected manufacturing activities with a more diversified competitive economy, Uzbekistan can achieve and benefit from WTO membership" [8].

Research methodology

This scientific article examines the necessity of Uzbekistan's membership in multilateral agreements for the state economy using a systematic comparative analysis and a systematic approach, expert and comparative analysis, analysis-synthesis, and other modern methods.

Analysis and results

The World Trade Organization (WTO) is an organization that discusses ways to solve trade-related problems of member countries. The basis of the WTO is its agreements, which are signed by the participants of the organization. The WTO was established in 1947 - the successor to GATT. Today, this organization has 166 member states, accounting for 98 percent of the world's gross domestic product. The WTO is an organization aimed at ensuring the primacy of the principle of "non-discrimination" in international trade in goods, services and intellectual property. Based on this principle, member states ensure that discrimination is not allowed among their trading partners, as well as between foreign and domestic manufacturers and service providers. As a result, each member state of the WTO, as an equal subject of international trade, conducts foreign economic and trade relations on the basis of the same opportunities as other members.

For our country, WTO membership will further increase the potential of the country's economy, making Uzbekistan an important link in the global production and value-added chain. Also, the issue of Uzbekistan's full membership in the World Trade Organization is included as one of the most important goals in the "Uzbekistan - 2030" strategy. In a short period of time, in order to harmonize national legislation with WTO agreements, 24 regulatory legal acts were adopted during 2023-2024, and about 40 documents were harmonized. As a result of the intensification of meetings of working groups on accession to the WTO, active bilateral negotiations have been conducted with more than 30 countries today, of which all conditions for market access have been agreed with 11 countries [17].

According to statistical data for 2023, Uzbekistan has established import relations with 129 WTO member states and export relations with 137 countries [11]. In 2023, the foreign trade turnover of our Republic amounted to 62.5 billion US dollars. This figure increased by 12.0 billion US dollars or 23.9% compared to the same period in 2022. The composition of trade turnover is as follows: exports amounted to 24.4 billion US dollars, and imports amounted to 38.1 billion US dollars [9].

Uzbekistan's trade relations with the World Trade Organization (WTO) member states have developed significantly in recent years. In particular, import relations with WTO member states have undergone significant changes. During 2019-2023, Uzbekistan's import volume with WTO member states increased significantly. These changes reflect the need to expand and diversify Uzbekistan's economic relations in global markets. In 2023, Uzbekistan's import volume with WTO member states reached 75.1%, which indicates a high share of these countries in the country's foreign trade. In 2019, imports from WTO member states amounted to 71.5%, and in 2020 this figure increased to 73.6%. In 2021 and 2022, the share of imports was relatively stable, amounting to 73.7% and 74%. In 2023, this share reached 75.1%. This indicator confirms the important role of WTO member states in our country's foreign trade.

From the table below (Table 1), we can see that Uzbekistan's import relations have shown significant changes over the period 2019-2023. The main importing countries are countries such as China, Russia, Kazakhstan, and South Korea, as well as developed and developing economies and economic partners such as Turkey, Germany, Brazil, India, France, and the United States.

In 2023, Uzbekistan's imports from China amounted to \$11.34 billion, from Russia to \$6.66 billion, from Kazakhstan to \$3.07 billion, and from South Korea to \$2.31 billion. Import relations with these countries are of great importance, as they are Uzbekistan's main partners in technology, industrial equipment, energy products, raw materials, and other important resources.

The increase in imports with major economies such as China and Russia is mainly driven by imports of energy, industrial equipment, automobiles, electronics, chemicals, and construction materials. China's share in imports has grown significantly by 2023, reaching \$11.34 billion. This indicates the need to further strengthen Uzbekistan's import policy towards China. Changes in Uzbekistan's import relations are closely related to the country's foreign trade policy updates.

Table 1

Import relations of the Republic of Uzbekistan with WTO member states¹ (in million US dollars)

<u>№</u>	<u>Countries</u>	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
1	China	5 108,63	4 501,22	4 923,42	6 427,71	11 339,10
2	Russia	4 137,69	4 173,78	5 462,24	6 230,69	6 660,63
3	Kazakhstan	1 942,01	2 097,35	2 742,18	3 243,51	3 068,54
4	South Korea	2 664,82	2 099,37	1 841,06	2 299,78	2 313,47
5	Turkey	1 326,41	1 087,27	1 717,58	1 738,54	1 897,74
6	German	927,53	759,37	693,51	1 071,30	985,50
7	Brazil	115,50	89,17	348,23	553,37	652,28
8	India	330,57	423,03	460,57	655,06	649,11
9	France	140,51	132,51	259,53	271,67	595,00
10	USA	567,24	248,48	365,48	368,73	512,01
As percentage of total imports		71,5	73,6	73,7	74,0	75,1

¹ Analyzed by the author based on data from the Statistical Agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Uzbekistan's main imports from WTO member states:

– Technology and industrial equipment: Technological products, industrial equipment and automotive products imported from China, South Korea, Germany and the United States play an important role in Uzbekistan's industrial sector.

– Energy resources: Oil, gas, coal and other energy resources imported from Russia and Kazakhstan meet Uzbekistan's energy needs.

– Agricultural products: Food and agricultural products imported from Kazakhstan, Turkey and Brazil play an important role in ensuring Uzbekistan's food security.

– Chemicals and industrial materials: Chemical industry products, construction materials, polymers and other industrial materials are used in various industrial sectors of Uzbekistan.

Uzbekistan's export relations with WTO member states have undergone significant changes in 2019-2023. During these years, the volume and composition of Uzbekistan's exports have changed significantly,

new markets have opened, and relations with existing partners have been strengthened.

Looking at the export dynamics of our republic, Uzbekistan's export relations with WTO member states have undergone changes over the years 2019-2023. According to statistics, the main export partners of Uzbekistan remain Russia, China, Kazakhstan and Turkey. In 2023, exports to Russia amounted to 3.5 billion US dollars, while exports to China exceeded 2.5 billion US dollars. Other important export markets of Uzbekistan include Afghanistan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, France, Pakistan and the United States (Table 2).

We can see that in 2023, the total volume of exports with WTO member states amounted to 48 percent, the change in this indicator for different countries requires diversification of Uzbekistan's foreign trade strategy. The decline in the share of Uzbekistan's exports is associated with the global economic situation, in particular the impact of the pandemic, and changes in demand in its markets. At the same time, there is an increasing need to diversify many sectors of exports, discover new markets, and strengthen existing ties.

Table 2

Export relations of the Republic of Uzbekistan with WTO member states² (in million US dollars)

№	Countries	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
1	Russia	2 531,87	1 485,76	2 088,24	3 151,10	3 495,68
2	China	2 528,75	1 937,05	2 529,09	2 632,00	2 486,56
3	Kazakhstan	1 392,96	908,42	1 178,38	1 407,55	1 417,05
4	Turkey	1 217,63	1 018,99	1 692,38	1 643,45	1 263,33
5	Afghanistan	616,96	776,74	667,48	756,28	857,24
6	Kyrgyzstan	669,64	760,46	792,04	982,54	634,44
7	Tajikistan	327,56	405,12	501,90	522,12	608,30
8	France	214,74	89,72	21,28	72,62	400,44
9	Pakistan	97,94	98,55	130,07	185,16	269,27
10	USA	36,65	28,50	60,79	124,48	253,12
As percentage of total exports		55,2	49,7	57,8	59,4	48,0

The main components of Uzbekistan's exports are:

– Agricultural products: Uzbekistan's exports are largely based on agricultural products, especially cotton, fruits and vegetables, rice, grains and other food products. Countries such as Russia, China, Kazakhstan, Turkey and Afghanistan are the main markets for Uzbekistan's agricultural exports.

– Textile products: Uzbekistan's textile industry also occupies an important place in terms of export volume. Textile products are exported to China, Turkey, Russia and the United States.

– Industrial products and machinery: Uzbekistan's exports of industrial products, especially construction

materials and machinery, also occupy an important place. Russia, Kazakhstan and Turkey are the markets for Uzbekistan's industrial exports.

Uzbekistan's import relations with the EAEU member states showed significant growth in 2019-2023. In 2023, Uzbekistan's import volume with the EAEU member states amounted to 13.6 billion US dollars. If import relations with the EAEU member states accounted for 26.8% of total imports in 2019, by 2023 this share will be 27.8%. This indicator reflects changes in the country's foreign trade policy, the development of cooperation with the EAEU, and the growth of import needs (Table 3).

² Analyzed by the author based on data from the Statistical Agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Table 3

Import relations of the Republic of Uzbekistan with the EAEU member states³ (in million US dollars)

No	Countries	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
1	Russia	4 137,7	4 173,8	5 462,2	6 230,7	6 660,6
2	Kazakhstan	1 942,0	2 097,3	2 742,2	3 243,5	3 068,5
3	Belarus	283,9	219,5	319,2	411,6	525,8
4	Kyrgyzstan	150,7	146,7	161,6	280,7	333,8
5	Armenia	2,5	2,9	3,0	5,1	9,5
As percentage of total imports		26,8	31,4	34,1	33,1	27,8

The total volume and share of Uzbekistan's export relations with the EAEU member states showed changes in 2019-2023. In 2023, the share of total exports with the EAEU member states amounted to 23.4%. This is a decrease from 26.6% in 2019, but a decrease in the share of exports compared to 2022 (29.1%). These changes are mainly due to the volume and diversification of Uzbekistan's exports to other regions. In 2019, exports to the EAEU member states

amounted to 26.6%, while in 2020 this figure decreased to 21.2%. In 2021, the share of exports increased to 24.8% and reached 29.1% in 2022. In 2023, this figure was 23.4%. Uzbekistan's export relations with the EAEU member states changed over the period 2019-2023, showing a number of increases and decreases. Russia, Kazakhstan and Kyrgyzstan constitute the main export markets of Uzbekistan (Table 4).

Table 4

Export relations of the Republic of Uzbekistan with the EAEU member states⁴ (in million US dollars)

No	Countries	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
1	Russia	2 531,9	1 485,8	2 088,2	3 099,1	3 495,7
2	Kazakhstan	1 393,0	908,4	1 178,4	1 393,1	1 417,1
3	Kyrgyzstan	669,6	760,5	792,0	978,4	634,4
4	Belarus	48,9	42,6	59,6	127,9	128,9
5	Armenia	2,8	4,2	10,4	19,9	31,9
As percentage of total exports		26,6	21,2	24,8	29,1	23,4

From the above analysis, we can see that Uzbekistan's trade relations with WTO member states are changing significantly from year to year. In the country, about 75% of imports and an average of 40-45% of exports during the year are accounted for by WTO member states.

The foreign trade turnover of our republic with the countries that are members of the Eurasian Economic Union amounted to 25.4% in 2023. It should be noted that the movement of goods and services, the movement of migrants and the movement of capital are ensured between the member states of the Eurasian Economic Union (Russia, Belarus, Kazakhstan, Armenia and the Kyrgyz Republic), and a common economic territory with a single customs system has been formed.

Conclusion

In conclusion, Uzbekistan's WTO membership creates good opportunities for the development of exports and imports on a global scale. In 2023, the share of imports with WTO member states amounted to 75.1%, which indicates that they constitute the main part of imports. The development of import relations with major economies such as China, Russia, South Korea and Turkey will satisfy Uzbekistan's needs for industrial, technological and consumer products. At the same time, the share of exports with WTO member states amounted to 48%, which will allow us to supply emerging markets with Uzbekistan's export products.

Membership in the EAEU will help Uzbekistan strengthen regional cooperation. The share of imports with EAEU member states will be 27.8% in 2023. Trade relations with countries participating in the Eur-

³ Analyzed by the author based on data from the Statistical Agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

⁴ Analyzed by the author based on data from the Statistical Agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

asian economic integration process, such as Russia, Kazakhstan and Belarus, are being strengthened. Exports with EAEU member states also amounted to 23.4%, and basic products such as cotton, textiles and fruits and vegetables occupy an important place in the structure of Uzbekistan's exports.

For Uzbekistan, WTO membership plays an important role in ensuring diversification and technological development in world markets. It creates opportunities for strengthening trade relations with China and Russia, exporting highly competitive products in various sectors.

Membership in the EAEU is mainly useful for deepening economic ties in the region and expanding trade with neighboring countries such as Russia and Kazakhstan. It creates stable markets for products such as cotton and fruits and vegetables.

For Uzbekistan, WTO membership is more advantageous in terms of long-term strategic prospects. Because:

- WTO membership increases access to international markets.
- Creates a reliable platform for attracting foreign investment.
- Diversification of products and services allows for an increase in the share of high value-added products.

At the same time, it is advisable to strengthen ties with the EAEU and take advantage of regional economic benefits through effective trade policies. Rather than becoming a full member of the EAEU, maintaining preferential trade agreements with the union may be a more flexible strategy for Uzbekistan. This will help to obtain regional benefits without limiting cooperation with the WTO.

Literature

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the Strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan "Uzbekistan-2030", No. DP-158 dated 11.09.2023: National Database of Legislative Information, 12.09.2023, No. 06/23/158/0694; 29.12.2023, No. 06/23/214/0984
2. Larch, M., Monteiro, J.A., Piermartini, R. and Yotov, Y., 2019. On the effects of GATT/WTO membership on trade: They are positive and large after all.

3. Tang, M.K., and Wei, S.J. (2009). "The value of making commitments externally: Evidence from WTO accessions". *Journal of International Economics* 78(2): 216–29.

4. Allee, T.L. and Scalera, J.E., 2012. The divergent effects of joining international organizations: Trade gains and the rigors of WTO accession. *International Organization*, 66(2), pp.243-276.

5. Drabek, Z. and Bacchetta, M., 2004. Tracing the Effects of WTO Accession on Policy-making in Sovereign States: Preliminary Lessons from the Recent Experience of Transition Countries. *World Economy*, 27(7), pp.1083-1125.

6. Felbermayr, G. and Kohler, W., 2010. Modeling the extensive margin of world trade: new evidence on GATT and WTO membership. *The World Economy*, 33(11), pp.1430-1469.

7. Eicher, T.S. and Henn, C., 2011. In search of WTO trade effects: Preferential trade agreements promote trade strongly, but unevenly. *Journal of International Economics*, 83(2), pp.137-153.

8. Richard Pomfret, 2020. Uzbekistan and the World Trade Organization. <https://iit.ade-laide.edu.au/ua/media/726/uzbekistan-wto.pdf>

Internet websites

9. Official website of the Statistical Agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan: www.stat.uz URL

10. Official website of the WTO: www.wto.org URL

11. <https://stat.uz/uz/rasmiy-statistika/merchandise-trade-2>

12. https://www.wto.org/english/thewto_e/whatis_e/tif_e/org6_e.htm

13. https://www.wto.org/english/thewto_e/whatis_e/who_we_are_e.htm

14. <https://stat.uz/uz/matbuot-markazi/qo-mitayangiliklar/57551-o-zbekiston-respublikasi-tashqi-savdo-aylanmasi-2024-yil-yanvar-iyun-4>

15. https://www.wto.org/english/thewto_e/whatis_e/tif_e/org6_e.htm

16. https://www.wto.org/english/thewto_e/whatis_e/who_we_are_e.htm

17. <https://parliament.gov.uz/news/iqtisodiyot-rivojiga-yanada-keng-yol-ochiladi>